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Numerology (II)
or
Properties of Numbers

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1) Factorial base:

0, 1, 10, 11, 20, 21, 100, 101, 110, 111, 120, 121, 200, 201, 210, 211, 220, 221, 300, 301, 310, 311, 320, 321, 1000, 1001, 1010, 1011, 1020, 1021, 1100, 1101, 1110, 1111, 1120, 1121, 1200, ...

(Each number n written in the factorial base.)

(We define over the set of natural numbers the following infinite base: for $k \geq 1 f_k = k!$)

It is proved that every positive integer A may be uniquely written in the factorial base as:

$$A = (\overline{a_n \dots a_2 a_1})_{(F)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i f_i, \text{ with all } a_i = 0, 1, \dots, i \text{ for } i \geq 1.$$

in the following way:

- if $f_n \leq A < f_{n+1}$ then $A = f_n + r_1$;

- if $f_m \leq r_1 < f_{m+1}$ then $r_1 = f_m + r_2, m < n$;

and so on until one obtains a rest $r_j = 0$.

What's very interesting: $a_1 = 0$ or 1 ; $a_2 = 0, 1$, or 2 ; $a_3 = 0, 1, 2$ or 3 , and so on...

If we note by $f(A)$ the superior factorial part of A (i.e. the largest factorial less than or equal to A), then A is written in the factorial base as:

$$A = f(A) + f(A - f(A)) + f(A - f(A) - f(A - f(A))) + \dots$$

Rules of addition and subtraction in factorial base:

for each digit a_i we add and subtract in base $i + 1$, for $i \geq 1$.

For example, addition:

base	5	4	3	2	
		2	1	0	+
		2	2	1	
		1	1	0	1

because: $0 + 1 = 1$ (in base 2);

$1 + 2 = 10$ (in base 3); therefore we write 0 and keep 1;

$2 + 2 + 1 = 11$ (in base 4).

Now subtraction:

base	5	4	3	2	
	1	0	0	1	-
			3	2	0
			1	1	

because: $1 - 0 = 1$ (in base 2);

$0 - 2 = ?$ it's not possible (in base 3), go to the next left unit, which is 0 again (in base 4), go again to the next left unit, which is 1 (in base 5), therefore $1001 \rightarrow 0401 \rightarrow 0331$ and then $0331 - 320 = 11$.

Find some rules for multiplication and division.

In a general case:

if we want to design a base such that any number

$A = (\overline{a_n \dots a_2 a_1})_{(B)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i$, with all $a_i = 0, 1, \dots, t_i$ for $i \geq 1$, where all $t_i \geq 1$, then: this base should be

$$b_1 = 1, b_{i+1} = (t_i + 1) * b_i \text{ for } i \geq 1.$$

2) More general-sequence sieve:

For $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, let $u_i > 1$, be a strictly increasing positive integer sequence, and $v_i < u_i$ another positive integer sequence. Then:

From the natural numbers set:

- keep the v_1 -th number among $1, 2, 3, \dots, u_1 - 1$, and delete every u_1 -th numbers;

- keep the v_2 -th number among the next $u_2 - 1$ remaining numbers, and delete every u_2 -th numbers;

... and so on, for step $k (k \geq 1)$:

-keep the v_k -th number among the next $u_k - 1$ remaining numbers, and delete every u_k -th numbers;

...

Problem: study the relationship between sequences $u_i, v_i, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, and the remaining sequence resulted from the more general sieve.

u_i and v_i previously defined, are called sieve generators.

4) Mobile periodicals (II):

... 0000000000000000000000000010000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000001100000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011211000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000001000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011211000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011232110000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011234321100000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011232110000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011234321100000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011211000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011000000000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011232110000000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011234321100000000000000000000000000000 ...
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... 0000000000000000000000000011234543211000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011234543211000000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011234565432110000000000000000000000000 ...
... 0000000000000000000000000011234565432110000000000000000000000000 ...
.....

This sequence has the form

$$\underbrace{1, 111, 11211, 111, 1, 111, 11211, 1123211, 11211, 111, 1, 111, 11211, 1123211, 112343211, \dots}_{5 \qquad 7 \qquad 9}$$

- divide B by k , and write the integer part of the quotient B_1 on the column $c(B)$;
 ... and so on with the new numbers A_1 and B_1 , until we get a $B_i < k$ on the column $c(B)$;
 Then:

- write another column $c(r)$, on the right side of $c(B)$, such that:

for each number of column $c(B)$, which may be a multiple of k plus the rest r (where $r = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k - 1$), the corresponding number on $c(r)$ will be r ;

- multiply each number of column A by its corresponding r of $c(r)$, and put the new products on another column $c(P)$ on the right side of $c(r)$;

- finally add all numbers of column $c(P)$.

$A \times B =$ the sum of all numbers of $c(P)$.

Remark that any multiplication of integer numbers can be done only by multiplication with $2, 3, \dots, k$, division by k , and additions.

This is a generalization of Russian multiplication (where $k = 2$).

This multiplication is usefull when k is very small, the best values being for $k = 2$ (Russian multiplication - known since Egyptian time), or $k = 3$. If k is greater than or equal to $\min\{10, B\}$, this multiplication is trivial (the obvious multiplication).

Example 1. (if we choose $k = 3$):

$$73 \times 97 = ?$$

x_3	/3		
$c(A)$	$c(B)$	$c(r)$	$c(P)$
73	97	1	73
219	32	2	438
657	10	1	657
1971	3	0	0
5913	1	1	5913
			7081 total

therefore: $73 \times 97 = 7081$.

Remark that any multiplication of integer numbers can be done only by multiplication with $2, 3$, divisions by 3 , and additions.

Example 2. (if we choose $k = 4$):

$$73 \times 97 = ?$$

x_4	/4		
$c(A)$	$c(B)$	$c(r)$	$c(P)$
73	97	1	73
292	24	0	0
1168	6	2	2336
4672	1	1	4672
			7081 total

therefore: $73 \times 97 = 7081$.

Remark that any multiplication of integer numbers can be done only by multiplication with 2, 3, 4, divisions by 4, and additions.

Example 3. (if we choose $k = 5$):

$73 \times 97 = ?$

x_5	/5		
$c(A)$	$c(B)$	$c(r)$	$c(P)$
73	97	2	146
365	19	4	1460
1825	3	3	5475
			7081 total

therefore: $73 \times 97 = 7081$.

Remark that any multiplication of integer numbers can be done only by multiplication with 2, 3, 4, 5, divisions by 5, and additions.

This multiplication becomes less usefull when k increases.

Look at another example (4), what happens when $k = 10$:

Example 4. $73 \times 97 = ?$

x_{10}	/10		
$c(A)$	$c(B)$	$c(r)$	$c(P)$
73	97	7	511 (= 73×7)
730	9	9	6570 (= 73×9)
			7081 total

therefore: $73 \times 97 = 7081$.

Remark that any multiplication of integer numbers can be done only by multiplication with 2, 3, ..., 10, divisions by 10, and additions - hence we obtain just the obvious multiplication!

11) Division by k^n :

Another way to divide an integer numbers A by k^n , where k, n are integers ≥ 2 :

- write A and k^n on two different vertical columns: $c(A)$, respectively $c(k^n)$;
- divide A by k , and write the integer quotient A_1 on the column $c(A)$;
- divide k^n by k , and write the quotient $q_1 = k^{n-1}$ on the column $c(k^n)$;
- ... and so on with the new numbers A_1 and q_1 , until we get $q_n = 1 (= k^0)$ on the column $c(k^n)$;

Then:

- write another column $c(r)$, on the left side of $c(A)$, such that:
 - for each number of column $c(A)$, which may be multiple of k plus the rest r (where $r = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1$), the corresponding number on $c(r)$ will be r ;
- write another column $c(P)$, on the left side of $c(r)$, in the following way: the element on line i (except the last line which is 0) will be k^{i-1} ;
- multiply each number of column $c(P)$ by its corresponding r of $c(r)$, and put the new products on another column $c(R)$ on the left side of $c(P)$;
- finally add all numbers of column $c(R)$ to get the final rest R , while the final quotient will be stated in front of $c(k^n)$'s 1.

Therefore:

$$A/(k^n) = A_n \text{ and rest } R_n.$$

Remark that any division of an integer number by k^n can done only by divisions to k , calculations of powers of k , multiplications with 1, 2, ..., $k-1$, additions.

This division is usefull when k is small, the best values being when k is an one-digit number, and n large. If k is very big and n very small, this division becomes useless.

Example 1. $1357/(2^7) = ?$

			/2	/2	
$c(R)$	$c(P)$	$c(r)$	$c(A)$	$c(2^7)$	
1	2^0	1	1357	2^7	line ₁
0	2^1	0	678	2^6	line ₂
4	2^2	1	339	2^5	line ₃
8	2^3	1	169	2^4	line ₄
0	2^4	0	84	2^3	line ₅
0	2^5	0	42	2^2	line ₆
64	2^6	1	21	2^1	line ₇
			10	2^0	last_line
77					

Therefore: $1357/(2^7) = 10$ and rest 77.

Remark that the division of an integer number by any power of 2 can be done only by divisions to 2, calculations of power of 2, multiplications and additions.

Example 2. $19495/(3^8) = ?$

			/3	/3	
$c(R)$	$c(P)$	$c(r)$	$c(A)$	$c(3^8)$	
1	3^0	1	19495	3^8	line ₁
0	3^1	0	6498	3^7	line ₂
0	3^2	0	2166	3^6	line ₃
54	3^3	2	722	3^5	line ₄
0	3^4	0	240	3^4	line ₅
486	3^5	2	80	3^3	line ₆
1458	3^6	2	26	3^2	line ₇
4374	3^7	2	8	3^1	line ₈
			2	3^0	last_line
6373					

Therefore: $19495/(3^8) = 2$ and rest 6373.

Remark that the division of an integer number by any power of 3 can be done only by divisions to 3, calculations of power of 3, multiplications and additions.

References

[1] Alain Bouvier et Michel George, sous la direction de Francois Le Lionnais, "Dictionnaire des Mathematiques", Presses Universitaires de France, Paris, 1979, p. 659;

"The Florentin Smarandache papers" special collection, Arizona State University, Tempe, AZ 85287.

12) Almost prime of first kind:

$a_1 \geq 2$, and for $n \geq 1$ a_{n+1} is the smallest number that is not divisible by any of the previous terms (of the sequence) $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$.

Example for $a_1 = 10$:

10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 21, 23, 25, 27, 29, 31, 35, 37, 41, 43, 47, 49, 53, 57, 61, 67, 71, 73, ...

If one starts by $a_1 = 2$, it obtains the complete prime sequence and only it.

If one starts by $a_2 > 2$, it obtains after a rank r , where $a_r = p(a_1)^2$ with $p(x)$ the strictly superior prime part of x , i.e. the largest prime strictly less than x , the prime sequence:

- between a_1 and a_r , the sequence contains all prime numbers of this interval and some composite numbers;

- from a_{r+1} and up, the sequence contains all prime numbers greater than a_r and no composite numbers.

13) Almost primes of second kind:

$a_1 \geq 2$, and for $n \geq 1$ a_{n+1} is the smallest number that is coprime with all of the previous terms (of the sequence) $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$.

This second kind sequence merges faster to prime numbers than the first kind sequence.

Example for $a_1 = 10$:

10, 11, 13, 17, 19, 21, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 57, 61, 67, 71, 73, ...

If one starts by $a_1 = 2$, it obtains the complete prime sequence and only it.

If one starts by $a_2 > 2$, it obtains after a rank r , where $a_r = p_i p_j$ with p_i and p_j prime number strictly less than and not dividing a_1 , the prime sequence:

- between a_1 and a_r , the sequence contains all prime numbers of this interval and some composite numbers;

- from a_{r+1} and up, the sequence contains all prime numbers greater than a_r and no composite numbers.